

Country status	Under developing
Total labor force (2005)	496.4 million
% of labor force in agriculture	60%
% of labor force in industry sector	17%
% of labor force in service sector	23%
Unemployment rate	8.90%
Population below poverty line (2008)	29%
Total exports f.o.b.(2005)in USD billion	99.45
Total imports f.o.b.(2005) in USD billion	138.09
Net exports f.o.b.(2005) in USD billion	-38.64
Total Investment (gross fixed) (2005)	28.1% GDP
Industrial production growth rate (2005)	7.90%
Forex reserves and gold	USD 136 billion
Official exchange rate(2005)	Rs.44.1011 per USD
No. of airports	341
Internet users	60.0 million
Constitution of the government	Federal republic
History	Was Portuguese colony & got independence in 1822
Natural resources	Coal, iron ore, manganese, mica, bauxite, NG, limestone, diamond, Petroleum, arable land

Source: The little green and red book series of world bank and FAO statistical year book series of UN publications

Literature review :

Literature discussed in this chapter, which throws light on the contributions made by some of the prominent researchers in this study area, will set the guidelines for this particular research project and indicate the tremendous scope for the further research in this particular area. Literature available pertaining to subject matter of this research work is being discussed in brief.

NFI Archive Report (2003), reported that the fruits and vegetables that are grown only on 6-7 percent of gross cropped area have contributed more than 18.8 percent of the gross value of agricultural output and 52% export earnings out of total agricultural produce. They further opined that during the last few years considerable emphasis has been given to this sector. Accordingly, areas under fruit production has increased by 172 percent from 1961-1993, productivity per hectare was nearly doubled leading to an increase in production to the tune of 320 percent. The average labor requirement for fruit production is 860 man-days per hectare per annum as against 143 man-days for cereals crops. Crops like grapes, bananas, and pineapple generates much larger employment roughly from 1000 to 2500 man-days per hectare per annum, the researcher added.

MOFPI (Ministry of Food Processing Industries) Report, (1999), reported that India is the largest producer

significant negative growth. Overall growth is unattractive and discouraging. Indian processors have to look for different applications of this intermediary product. This calls for possessing state of the art R&D facilities. Indian processors should invest heavily in building necessary R&D facilities.

Higher value addition to existing products, strengthening the R&D base, and scouting for various applications for the intermediary products are some of the important critical success factors for Indian fruit processing industry.

Indian fruit processing industry should follow the footsteps of Brazilian fruit processing industry in this regard and turn it in to the most vibrant and fast growing industry of India.

Conclusion :

From the above findings following conclusions can be drawn.

1. Significant portion (nearly 80%) of the total exports undertaken by the mango processing industry falls in to only one category, i.e. pulp.
2. The detailed analysis of the CGR of exports of other processed mango products reveal that there is great demand for the value added products like; mango kernel nuts broken, mango sliced and dried, mango squash, mango juice, jams jellies and marmalades', etc. (CGR ranges from 79% to 20%).
3. Indian mango processors have primarily targeted gulf countries (Middle East Asian countries) for exports and as the findings reveal the value realized from the exports to such countries is not very attractive.

Recommendations :

1. Hence Indian mango processors should start manufacturing high value added processed mango products and export them to rich countries like; USA, UK, Canada, Australia, other European countries so that value realization will be much higher. To achieve this Indian mango processors must improve their quality standards and bring in lot of innovation to meet the stringent quality standards set by importing countries (like FDA standards of US). Indian fruit processors must also invest a lot in R and D facilities and activities and come out with innovative products and technologies.
2. Indian mango processors should also think of utilizing the byproducts like mango kernels so that total processing loss can be curtailed. Many innovative products like; mango margarine, facial cream, other cosmetic products, piggery feed ingredient, etc. can be produced using mango kernel oil and mango kernel flour. This will further strengthen the profitability of the processors.
3. The ever increasing export demand for the specific processed mango products like; natural mango juice or squash, jams, etc., is one of the reasons for the supernatural growth of this sector in India and has lured the interests of many MNCs and SMEs to enter in to this sector. Yet Indian mango processing industry is still miles apart when we compare with the leading countries like Brazil and China. These countries have realized the tremendous potential that is being hidden in this specialized sector, i.e. mango processing industry, and are trying to exploit the same before any other country does. Well coordinated and integrated effort by all the stake holders involved, i.e., cultivators, processors, middle men, nodal bodies, Government Institutions, agriculture universities, etc., is the need of the hour to exploit the huge potential which this sector has.

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Sources of secondary information

1. The little green and red data book series by World Bank publications.
2. FAO production year book series by UN publications.
3. International Trade Center statistics from www.itc.com, the official website of ITC (International Trade Centre).
4. Official website of DGFT (Directorate General of Foreign Trade) of India.

